

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO YOUNG LEARNERS FROM THEIR YOUNG AGE

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***Annotation:** Learning language is getting more developed day by day and there is a fact that if children learn it in their early age, it will be much easier process, thus in this article I am going to give reasons about this wide-spread perception.*

***Key words:** primary curriculum, obligatory, constructive teaching, communicative teaching, activities, formal education.*

In recent years, with the influence of globalization and the increasing importance of English as an international language in world communication, many European and asian countries have taken steps to introduce the teaching of English to children at an earlier age. For instance, European union countries introduced English to their primary curriculum and the age of beginning instruction became in 2002. Similarly, foreign language policy has undergone changes in Turkey as well. Under the new law that took effect in 1997, and in a way renewed in 2005. It became obligatory for primary school students to start studying a foreign language as part of the core primary curriculum from Grade 4.

This new reform in Turkey necessitated a new foreign language education curriculum at primary level based on the constructivist and communicative perspectives. Accordingly, a new course in pre-service English Language Teaching programs at universities - “teaching English to young learners” was introduced and a series of in-service education seminars were organized by the Ministry of National Education to familiarize the English language teachers with the new curriculum goals and the constructivist and communicative teaching philosophies and to equip them with special skills to be able to teach young learners. Normally developing children can learn another language at an early age given sufficient exposure and intraction. A number of resource books on teaching English to young learners emphasize the

following principles all of which derive from recent theorizing in the field with a focus on classroom practice:

- Activities should be fun and enjoyable
- Activities should create a desire or need to communicate
- Young learners should feel relaxed in a classroom
- Language use should be illustrated by use of objects, pictures, actions or gestures.

When it comes to foreign language education in primary school, it means that classes on their own are not enough, if the child no longer has any contact with the language after school, anything they have learned will soon start to disappear, this applies to all school subjects, and particularly to foreign languages. So you need to encourage your child to use the words they learn as often as possible outside the classroom because the best way to learn any language is to use it. Of course, the role of parents can be crucial here. First the key thing is to motivate the child, not force them. When they are young, children acquire knowledge best in stress-free and pressure-free environments through play. Therefore, it is necessary to create a stimulating and supportive environment for learning a foreign language. A child should feel safe and protected and learn a second language outside of a school in a completely natural way, similar to the way they've acquired their native language. We need to praise and reward the child for everything they do right. If they encounter an obstacle, it is important to support them and overcome it together. If you feel the child is tired, let them have some rest and enjoy other activities. Simply, learning a language outside the classroom should be more like play than formal education. Include target language songs and chants throughout your day. These are great for quick warm-ups, cool downs and breaks between larger activities. Tell or read target language stories that engage their imaginations. To up the engagement level even further, go outside and teach movement vocabulary or nature vocabulary. Sometimes a change of scene and fresh air is all kids need to stay on track. Anyone who has ever raised one, been on an airplane with one or had one in the classroom knows how true this is. Of course, each individual child is unique and has their own balance of activity and energy, but if you are teaching young learners you can generally expect your students to outlast you every day of the week. In fact, requiring kids to sit for long periods of time actually makes them less able to learn.

So, working with this characteristic rather than against it is key in your language classroom. That is where total physical response comes into play. This teaching method is built on the idea of students using their bodies in response to foreign language instruction. The teacher gives an instruction in the target language and the students perform the action. A simple way to get started with total physical response is to share action-focused sentences with your class and demonstrate what they mean. Then have students repeat the same. Have your kids walk around and associate body movements with the language structures you are teaching.

References:

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